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D6.2

Communication kit description

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RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium	
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium	

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Abbreviations and Acronyms

Acronym	Definition
EC	European Commission
PO	Project officer
GA	Grant Agreement
WP	Work Package
ITS	Intelligent Transport Systems

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Executive Summary

This document is the description of the first update of the D6.2 Communication kit, which includes the development of the dissemination material consisted of the leaflet, the poster, the general presentation, the e-newsletters, the videos and the brochure. The communication kit is updated periodically and two other descriptions will be reported on M24 and M36 in the project timeline.

1. Introduction

During the first year of the INFRAMIX project, the communication kit aims to generally inform the public, relevant search, academic and industrial community on the project's general concept, including the objectives and expected results. This will be the basis for the further development of the communication kit and the communication and dissemination strategy in general, since the communication kit has already been produced on a large scale at this stage and will be updated periodically within the project's lifetime.

More specifically, the communication kit, as has been described, includes the project brochure, banner, general presentation, e-newsletters and finally promotional videos. This kit will be yearly updated (M12, M24, M36). In the second section is presented the dissemination kit as it is shaped and realized up to this moment.

2. Communication kit

2.1 INFRAMIX leaflet

The INFRAMIX leaflet was designed and published within TRA Conference 2018 in Vienna where INFRAMIX had a strong presence. More specifically, the leaflet included the objectives and the expected impact of the project, the traffic scenarios that will be investigated as well as images from the two test sites in Spain and in Austria (including pictures of its equipment). The main contact points (the project coordinator and the dissemination manager) of the project, the partners, the website and the INFRAMIX social media were also included in the leaflet. The leaflet was updated in the framework of ITS World Congress so as to include new pictures and elements which resulted from the project's evolution.

The general idea of the leaflet is to present the project briefly and in a comprehensible way so as to inform the targeted audiences about INFRAMIX. The leaflet is constantly updated according the projects' need and included in the online repository.

2.2 INFRAMIX banner

INFRAMIX banner has as objective to promote the project mainly in the scientific community and secondly in the general public. To reach this objective, the banner has been adjusted to the project's site in terms of language, text and visual elements. The first version of the INFRAMIX banner was developed and published in the TRA Conference 2018 in Vienna. It was designed in line with the INFRAMIX brand identity and the communication guidelines, has been updated in the framework of ITS World Congress and stored in the online repository. The banner includes information such as the INFRAMIX's general idea, the objectives, the expected impact and the interim major results as well as the partners, the main contact points, the website and the social media of INFRAMIX project.

The banner will be updated within the project's duration, in order to get aligned with the INFRAMIX presence on specific events. It will be used at conferences, exhibitions and public meetings.

2.3 INFRAMIX general presentation

In order to provide a homogenous image of the project to the external actors and the public, a standard presentation of the project has also been prepared and may be used by all partners to present or take some basic slides in order to prepare their individual presentations when participating in external events.

The presentation includes the following information: the INFRAMIX objectives and facts, the consortium, the main activities and the expected impact. It also provides all the information

to access the project's website and social media as well as to contact the project's representatives. The presentation has been stored in the online repository and will be updated regularly depending on the project's progress and the achieved results.

2.4 INFRAMIX e-newsletters

The project aims to publish periodic e-newsletter on important milestones of INFRAMIX in order to support the ongoing needs of the project after launching all the project's activities. The newsletter's objective is to summarize the project's activities and outcomes and to proactively initiate conversations with multiple stakeholders about on-going research topics. The e-newsletters include information about the project's process and will address both scientific community as well as SMEs and Industry. A mailing list has been created, including all the people that expressed their interest about INFRAMIX project and specifically its newsletter according to the recent GDPR rules. The [first INFRAMIX e-newsletter](#) has been issued and uploaded in the INFRAMIX website, as well as the online repository the consortium uses.

2.5 INFRAMIX promotional videos

The INFRAMIX project aims to provide videos so as to communicate the INFRAMIX messages in an easy and impactful way. The videos will be available on the project's website and social media, as well as on other available channels and platforms, such as YouTube, forums supporting the project's realization, the partners' websites e.t.c. The videos will be also displayed in relevant events and conferences which INFRAMIX will participate or organize.

Since the project runs the first year of its lifetime and does not have yet results to present in the video, our plan is to provide a more "promotional" video of the partners that participate in INFRAMIX and their affiliation to the project's activities, as well as the general information of the project.

The first INFRAMIX video has already been realized and presented in the English language. It is stored in the INFRAMIX account on YouTube in order to be available for all partners and visitors. It was also shown at the [ITS World Congress](#) 2018 at the project stand.

Given the fact that the first INFRAMIX video contains information about the partners and their activities, there was a long process for the partners to assure the approval to provide this material to the consortium. There were issues of ownership rights that had to be safeguarded. Therefore, there was a delay on the video development, in order the consortium to be totally vested.

2.6 INFRAMIX brochure

In addition with the project's leaflet, we decided to provide a more informative brochure. The INFRAMIX brochure has been developed and uploaded in the online repository. It is a 12 page booklet which contains extensive information of the project and its activities.

The INFRAMIX brochure will be distributed in different occasions and exhibitions to provide more specific information of the project. As we already have an INFRAMIX leaflet and due to our limited project results because of the first year of the project running, we have the flexibility to further improvements and edits on the brochure so as to secure an updated content.

3. Conclusion

In order to summarize, the INFRAMIX communication kit has been developed so as to

support all the communication and dissemination activities of the project. The general aim of the kit is to communicate the project, its activities and results in an effective way and make the results and deliverables of the project available on a comprehensible manner to all the potential audiences. The communication kit will be a live kit, which will be updated yearly as has been indicated in the Grant Agreement.

Annexes

INFRAMIX leaflet

@INFRAMIX INFRAMIX project

Partners
 austriatech ASFINAG
 Fraunhofer SIEMENS virtual vehicle
 Tomtom enjide autopistas

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Preparing road infrastructure for mixed vehicle traffic flows
www.inframix.eu

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no. 723014.

INFRAMIX is preparing the road infrastructure to support the coexistence of conventional and automated vehicles. The key outcome will be a hybrid road infrastructure able to handle the transition period and become the basis for future automated transport systems. To achieve this goal INFRAMIX will employ new advanced microscopic traffic flow models, advanced simulation techniques, innovative control strategies, as well as appropriate new and adapted existing physical and digital infrastructure elements. All these will be cross validated against user appreciation and safety performance leading among others to a novel road infrastructure classification scheme. The key elements of INFRAMIX are:

- Design new and upgrade existing physical & digital road infrastructure elements
- Develop a co-simulation environment
- Design and implement novel traffic estimation, monitoring and control strategies
- Develop hybrid testing system
- Design novel signaling and visualization elements
- Evaluate user's appreciation and acceptance
- Evaluate traffic safety
- Create a Road Infrastructure Classification Scheme

8 DIFFERENT USE CASES

Scenario 1: Dynamic Lane Assignment (incl. speed recommendations)
 1. Real time lane assignment under dynamic penetration rate of automated vehicles
 2. Exceptional circumstances e.g. adverse weather conditions
 3. A conventional vehicle drives on a dedicated lane for automated vehicles

Scenario 2: Roadworks zones
 4. Single lane closure (e.g. short term constructions)
 5. New lane design (e.g. long term constructions)

Scenario 3: Bottlenecks
 6. Automated vehicles driving behaviour adaptation in real time at signs
 7. Lane change advice to connected vehicles at bottlenecks
 8. Lane change advice combined with flow control at bottlenecks for all vehicles

EXPECTED IMPACT
 INFRAMIX will provide key elements for a step by step introduction of automated driving. A set of targeted interventions related to physical and digital infrastructure will be carefully defined, as road infrastructure has to deal with several challenges:

- The construction of new roads is expensive and time consuming
- Europe has already a quite mature road network
- Roads have a quite long lifecycle

The interventions will be adaptable and incremental to cope with a variety of existing infrastructure and diverse traffic scenarios.

Real tests on modern highways
 autopistas Girona (Spain)
 ASFINAG Graz (Austria)

INFRAMIX banner

INFRAMIX will help prepare road infrastructure to support the coexistence of conventional and automated vehicles.

Its main objective is to design, upgrade, adapt and test both physical and digital elements of the road infrastructure. The key outcome will be a "hybrid" road infrastructure able to handle the transition period and become the basis for future automated transport systems. The project developments will be validated via simulation and on real stretches of advanced highways. This will help to ensure that the proposed adaptations will not compromise safety, quality of service, efficiency and will be appreciated by the users.

INFRAMIX studies on three traffic scenarios: dynamic lane assignment, roadworks zones and bottlenecks. INFRAMIX addresses mainly highways, but the key results can also be transferred to urban roads.

Cases, expected impacts and interim major results

- Adaptation and development of simulation environments for mixed traffic scenarios
- Linking simulation environments to real traffic test sites (hybrid testing)
- Development, implementation and validation of traffic state estimation and traffic control algorithms for mixed vehicle traffic
- Specification of digital and physical elements (e.g. new visual signs) of the road infrastructure
- Evaluation of users' appreciation
- Evaluation of proposed INFRAMIX infrastructure measures with regards to traffic safety and efficiency
- Development of safety performance criteria for road infrastructure in mixed traffic
- Development of an infrastructure classification scheme for automated transport (similarly to the SAE levels of automation)
- Roadmap towards the long term vision of automated transport

Partners: austriatech, ASPINAG, Fraunhofer, SIEMENS, autostart, autopistas, enjde, TOMTOM

Project Coordinator: Austria's Federal Institute for Transport Infrastructure (BVI) / Marko Drenthaler, Head of International Dissemination Manager ENDE SOLUTIONS S.L. / David Quintana

INFRAMIX e-newsletter

Dear INFRAMIX follower,

We're thrilled to present to you our first INFRAMIX Newsletter, which includes:

- An overview of the successful participation of INFRAMIX at the TRAX2018 conference:
 - INFRAMIX participation highlights
 - INFRAMIX presentation at the session "Connected and Automated Transport – Automated transport: enabling methods and technologies" by Dr. Augustin Kienast
 - Dissemination material used during conference
- The latest updates from the project official deliverables:
 - CO-1 Requirements catalogue from the status quo analysis (*)
 - CO-2 Architecture and hardware specification of the simulation environment (*)
- A video of the state-of-the-art technology and equipment of the test site in Austria.

(*) This document has not yet been approved by the EC services

INFRAMIX is preparing the road infrastructure to support the transition period and the coexistence of conventional and automated vehicles. INFRAMIX main target is to design, upgrade, adapt and test (in simulation and in real-world) both physical and digital elements of the road infrastructure, to enable the coexistence of automated and conventional vehicles, in specific scenarios, ensuring an uninterrupted, predictable, safe and efficient traffic. The key outcome will be a "hybrid" road infrastructure able to handle the transition period and become the basis for future automated transport systems. Find more information about the project at <http://www.inframix.eu/>.

VIENNA 2018 TRA
A digital life for transport
Roadworks for safety, security and sustainability

<http://www.inframix.eu/>

INFRAMIX video

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fbU1FujU9u4>

INFRAMIX brochure

PARTNERS *austriatech* **ASFiNAG**

Fraunhofer FOKUS **SIEMENS** *Ingenuity for life* **virtual vehicle**

TOMTOM *enide* **autopistas**

We are on the Web!
www.inframix.eu

PROJECT FACTS
Project title: Road Infrastructure ready for mixed vehicle traffic flows
Starting Date: 01/06/2017
Duration: 36 Months
Budget (EU funding): 5.000.000 €

Coordinator
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 INFRAMIX project
 @inframix

INFRAMIX

Road infrastructure ready for mixed vehicle traffic flows

This project has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 720816.

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What is INFRAMIX?

INFRAMIX is an EU funded project in the framework of ARI-05-2016 'Road infrastructure to support the transition to automation and the coexistence of conventional and automated vehicles on the same network'. Its full title is 'Road Infrastructure ready for mixed vehicle traffic flows' and its duration is 36 Months (June 2017-May 2020).

Within the project, 11 partners collaborate targeting to design, upgrade, adapt and test both physical and digital elements of the road infrastructure, ensuring an uninterrupted, predictable, safe and efficient traffic.

To meet this high level objective INFRAMIX is working on different technologies, combining simulation, traffic flow modelling, traffic estimation and control algorithms e.t.c. This work includes ways of informing all types of vehicles about the control commands issued by the road operator and the proposal of new kind of visual and electronic signals for the needs of mixed scenarios.

The outcomes will be assessed via simulation and in real stretches of advanced Highways. Key aspects considered throughout the project will be to ensure that the proposed adaptations will not jeopardize safety, quality of service, efficiency and will be appreciated by the users.

To achieve its objectives INFRAMIX selects a bottom-up approach. Instead of working in generic solutions with questionable impact, it builds on three specific high value (in terms of importance for traffic efficiency and safety) traffic scenarios, namely "dynamic lane assignment", "roadworks zones" and "bottlenecks".

INFRAMIX | Seite 1

03 Which are the INFRAMIX objectives?

- Design new and update existing physical & digital road infrastructure elements;
- Develop a co-simulation environment combining the modelling of the vehicle behaviour with the traffic simulation to examine mixed traffic scenarios under various penetration rates of automated vehicles
- Design and implement novel traffic estimation, monitoring and control strategies;
- Develop hybrid testing system: coupling infrastructure elements and vehicles on real roads with virtual traffic environment including representative mixed traffic situations
- Design novel signaling and visualization elements;
- Evaluate traffic safety and user's appreciation;
- Create a Road Infrastructure Classification Scheme

Short-term vision

Long-term vision

INFRAMIX | Seite 3

08 Road infrastructure ready for mixed vehicle traffic flow | Volume 1, Issue 1

The Spanish test site is located within the Mediterranean Corridor between Barcelona and the French border. The specific highway segment is over 20km of four-lane carriageway. Each lane is 3,5m wide. The internal hard shoulder is 1m and the external hard shoulder is 2,5m. The highway median is 5m wide (in average). The test site includes four intersections and a 180m tunnel. The Average Daily Traffic (ADT) in this section was around 30,000 vehicles per day in 2016, and the speed limit is 120km/h.

The currently available ITS equipment includes different types of VMSs, video cameras, Bluetooth antennas, and magnetic sensors for measuring occupancy and 1 Weather station, ITS-G5 short range communication and cellular communication are available at the test-site, and a proprietary Fibre Optic ring network with 10 Gb bandwidth connects all the equipment from the test-site to the TMC in real-time.

INFRAMIX, MARCA, TUM, INRAEAD 10 | 10091 1007

09

The Austrian Test Site includes 20km of A2 motorway between LaBnitzhöhe and City of Graz. The test site is equipped with gantries, mobile VMS, roadworks warning equipment, ITS-G5 K51L, video cameras (traffic management, single vehicle detection), single-vehicle counters, environmental sensors and radar detection. It enables testing of newly developed visual information, ITS-G5 short-range communication, cellular communication and real-time communication with the traffic control center. The infrastructure is based on a fibre-optic network that provides IP-based network connectivity to gantries.

The additional intention of the Austrian test site is to provide for each test run the complete precise trajectories of the tested vehicle as well as all vehicles in the surrounding traffic for the testing party to analyse. The data can be played back via a 3-D simulation tool.

INFRAMIX, MARCA, TUM, INRAEAD 11 | 10091 1007

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INFRAMIX expected impact

As the construction of new roads is an expensive and time consuming project while Europe has already a quite mature road network, and considering the fact that roads have a quite long lifecycle (especially compared with vehicles), **the only way to prepare our existing road network for automation is through targeted interventions both physical and digital.** This is even more important for the long transition period where we expect a step by step introduction of automation and mixed traffic on roads with different capabilities and installed equipment. In this respect, INFRAMIX is expected to have an important impact as it will deliver specific solutions with tangible integrated interventions, both physical and digital. These will be tested and validated beforehand through the use of innovative modeling technologies (new traffic flow models and advanced simulation tools)

guaranteeing this way their efficiency, traffic safety but also users' appreciation and acceptance.

this set of interventions will be adaptable and incremental to cope with a variety of existing infrastructure (old, new, etc.) and **diverse traffic scenarios** (percentage of automated vehicles, of connected vehicles etc.). The fact that they will also be tested in quite demanding scenarios **on the actual road networks** of the consortium partners will ensure that the proposed scenarios will be realistic and aligned with modern road design and engineering principles.

Moreover, INFRAMIX will propose a scheme for classifying road infrastructure into "automation-appropriate" levels by listing connectivity and automation capabilities of each road segment, while informing road users about its capability to host automated

INFRAMIX, MARCA, TUM, INRAEAD 10 | 10091 1007

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Key expected results

Road infrastructure for mixed traffic	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> New traffic signs for mixed traffic Novel traffic monitoring recommendations (wireless messages extensions)
Infrastructure Classification Scheme	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investigation of the infrastructure connectivity, automation capabilities, capacity to host vehicles of different levels of automation and connectivity A guide of how to incrementally upgrade levels of infrastructure to avoid stranded investments
Simulation platform	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Investigation of several cases with safety critical impact Testing of innovative traffic control algorithms With increased traffic densities in exceptional conditions With different roles of conventional and automated vehicles
Hybrid testing system	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Testing of new developments of connected and automated driving Emulation of critical traffic situation in a safe artificial environment

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INFRAMIX general presentation (indicative slides)

Road Infrastructure ready for mixed vehicle traffic flows

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 723016.

INFRAMIX project facts

Duration: 1 June 2017-31 May 2020
EC Funding: 5M €
Coordinator: AustriaTech
Consortium: AustriaTech, ICCS, Asfinag, Fraunhofer, Siemens, Virtual Vehicle, Abertis, Enide, Technical University of Crete, TomTom, BMW

Website: <https://www.inframix.eu/>
Social media: @inframix, inframix project

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Real tests

2 modern highways for real tests

Girona (Spain)

Gratz (Austria)

Traffic Scenarios	Spain	Austria	Hybrid testing	Co-simulation environment
Dynamic Lane Assignment	X			X
Roadworks		X	X	X
Bottlenecks	X	X	X	X

Keep track on INFRAMIX

- Website: <https://www.inframix.eu/>
- Twitter: @inframix
- Linkedin: inframix project
- Sign up to our newsletter: <https://lists.inframix.eu/wws/subscribe/news>
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